

Rac-3e

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-108-rac-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	0831
Vial:	101	Acq. Method Set:	20%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	xt 2 108 rac
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	12.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	8/30/2021 11:07:14 PM CST		
Date Processed:	8/31/2021 8:43:21 AM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	5.803	5669631	49.84	748228
2	8.808	5705109	50.16	460126

Asy-3e (DyKAT)

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-109-1-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	0831
Vial:	102	Acq. Method Set:	20%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	xt 2 109 1
Injection Volume:	10.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	12.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	8/30/2021 11:25:06 PM CST		
Date Processed:	8/31/2021 8:45:37 AM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	5.813	1287230	4.13	173133
2	8.812	29845166	95.87	2374603

Asy-3e (KR)

SAMPLE INFORMATION			
Sample Name:	xt-2-109-4-20%-AD	Acquired By:	System
Sample Type:	Unknown	Sample Set Name:	08312
Vial:	103	Acq. Method Set:	20%qb
Injection #:	1	Processing Method:	xt 2 109 4
Injection Volume:	4.00 ul	Channel Name:	254.0nm
Run Time:	12.0 Minutes	Proc. Chnl. Descr.:	2998 PDA 254.0 nm (2998)
Date Acquired:	8/31/2021 8:54:31 AM CST		
Date Processed:	8/31/2021 9:20:53 AM CST		

	RT	Area	% Area	Height
1	5.716	1029203	3.69	143929
2	8.609	26878910	96.31	2230543